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CREATIVITY OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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Abstract: First of all, the organization of independent education in the higher education system, determining the motivations that encourage students to work independently, and forming their independent learning skills is an urgent pedagogical problem. Because in the current conditions, where the range of information and knowledge is rapidly expanding, it is emphasized that all information cannot be fully delivered to students only during classes. By the nature of assignments, there are more types of independent work, and they have different educational goals: preliminary study of the material; listening to lectures, completing notes; working with recommended sources of information.

Key words: independent education, assignment, creativity, information, pedagogical problem, lesson activities, educational goals.

Annotatsiya: Avvalo, oliy ta'lim tizimida mustaqil ta'limni tashkil etish, talabani mustaqil ishlashiga undovchi motivlarni aniqlash, ularning mustaqil bilim olish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish dolzarb pedagogik muammo hisoblanadi. Chunki axborot va bilimlar doirasi tez sur'atlar bilan kengayib borayotgan hozirgi sharoitda barcha ma'lumotlarni faqat dars mashg'ulotlari paytida talabalarga to'liq yetkazib bo'lmasligi ta'kidlab o'tilgan. Topshiriqlarning tabiati bo'yicha mustaqil ishlarning ko'proq turlari mavjud va ular turli xil ta'lim maqsadlarini ko'zlaydi: materialni dastlabki o'rganish; ma'ruzalarni tinglash, eslatmalarni yakunlash; tavsiya etilgan axborot manbalari bilan ishlash.

Kalit so'zlar: mustaqil ta'lim, topshiriq, ijodkorlik, axborot, pedagogik muammo, dars mashg'ulotlari, ta'lim maqsadlari.

Аннотация: Прежде всего, организация самостоятельного обучения в системе высшего образования, определение мотивов, побуждающих студентов к самостоятельной работе, и формирование у них навыков самостоятельного обучения является актуальной педагогической проблемой. Потому что в современных условиях, когда спектр информации и знаний стремительно расширяется, подчеркивается, что вся информация не может быть полностью донесена до студентов только во время занятий. По характеру заданий видов самостоятельной работы больше, и они имеют разные учебные цели: предварительное изучение материала; прослушивание лекций, составление конспектов; работа с рекомендованными источниками информации.

Ключевые слова: самостоятельное обучение, задание, творчество, информация, педагогическая задача, деятельность урока, образовательные цели.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important tasks for higher education institutions today is to prepare knowledgeable, creative, and competitive professionals who meet global standards. The development or stagnation of a country depends on the degree of advancement of its education system. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on October 8, 2019 № DP-5847, "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"¹, prioritizes reforming higher education systematically, modernizing it, and adopting advanced teaching technologies based on international standards to enhance the quality of education.

To address these priorities, fostering independent learning among students has become a crucial requirement. Independent learning involves enabling students to engage deeply with study material, think critically, and solve problems independently. This method also encourages students to remain updated with recent trends and developments in their professional fields. By taking responsibility for their learning, students gain new knowledge and skills autonomously.

1 <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/6971334>

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues of organizing independent education in the educational process of students of higher educational institutions have been studied by B. Ziyamhammadov, J.G'. Yoldoshev, N.S. Sayidahmedov, and H. Karshibayev. The content of organizing students' independent work and the improvement of its teaching methodology have been researched by M. Barakayev, R. Jorayev, G.V. Zlotsky, G. Ivezia, S.I. Qulmamatov, M. Tojiyev, N.R. G'aybullayev, and D. Yunusova.

It is known that teaching students to work independently is the basis of their formation as mature specialists in their field in the future. The student will be able to make a plan to solve a problem independently based on the knowledge gained in lectures and practical sessions and implement it based on the plan. This can be a basis for a creative approach to development and intellectual growth. In most cases, students try to achieve the necessary level of knowledge from each lesson. However, if the independent work process is properly organized, if sufficient conditions are created for students to work independently, and if access to modern technology is provided, students' independent mastery of the subject will be the fundamental basis of their education.

Well, what should be understood by the independent study of students? In general, this can be said to be any activity related to training the thinking of the owner of the profession. Therefore, I believe in the guidance of teaching in the classroom and outside the classroom, which increases the cognitive activity of the student and encourages them to think independently. This can be said to be the sum of training.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The organization of independent education in the higher education system, the determination of motivations that encourage students to work independently, and the formation of their independent learning skills are significant challenges. In today's rapidly expanding world of information and knowledge, it is impossible to fully convey all necessary information solely through lectures. Experiments show that students deeply absorb knowledge only when they are actively engaged and work on themselves. Independent activity fosters creativity and critical thinking. Therefore, organizing the process of independent education for students and creating the necessary educational and methodological support for this purpose is a crucial task. In developed countries, the progress of society is closely linked to the advancement of higher education, and the development of modern information technologies further increases the need for independent education. This implies that the independent learning of students in educational institutions must be elevated to a new level.

The primary responsibility for guiding students' independent work and planning the process lies with the subject teacher. The structure of the lesson is determined by the teacher based on modern pedagogical technologies, and educational goals are clearly defined.² Students can develop self-management and control skills while designing the process of completing their independent work. In the curriculum for independent work, the tasks and objectives of the subject are thoroughly explained. Given the significant role of hardware and software in organizing students' independent work, the ability to perform such work effectively is essential. One of the urgent tasks is to study the laws related to the quality of information provision from a scientific and methodological perspective. In this context, special attention must be paid to educational and methodological literature, lecture texts, educational-methodological collections, standard educational documents, assignments, scientific tasks, research papers, and periodical publications. It is one of the examples that the efficiency of students' independent work depends on the thorough knowledge of science teachers from a methodological point of view and their pedagogical skills.³ Students who have experienced these qualities of the teacher often say: "The most important aspect of the teacher is that he makes everything clear and understandable. You will enjoy studying with such a teacher"; "The other one, however, is a teacher who is not suitable for anything, and I couldn't explain it clearly"; "He explains the educational material boringly and vaguely, as if there were some mechanisms in front of him, not living people."⁴

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Professional skill, in our current understanding, is not only the ability to deliver knowledge to the minds of students in an easier, more comprehensive, and understandable way but also the ability to manage the independent work of students, their cognitive activity intelligently and skillfully, and direct them in the right

2 Koysinov O.A, Muslimov N.A. Theory and methodology of organizing independent learning in the training of vocational teachers. Monograph. -T.: "Fan", 2009. - 92 p.

3 Ibragimova G.N. Development of creative thinking in students through interactive technologies in the higher education system // Modern education. 2017.№4. - P. 30.

4 Khudoynazarova M.F. Formation of students' creativity in the process of independent learning. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. April 2023 Issue 4 863 p

direction. Education that prepares students for creative activity must, first of all, arouse students' interest in the presented educational material. The use of problem-based learning in teaching is also effective in the formation of creative activity. Educational methods related to students' independent search and discovery of truth, along with heuristic or research methods, bring students to the "laboratory" of creative thinking.

The process involved is also of primary importance. Problem-based learning has several advantages in this respect: It teaches students logical, scientific, didactic, and creative thinking. It makes the learning material believable, thereby helping to turn knowledge into belief. It is usually very impressive and creates deep intellectual feelings, including high spirits, a sense of self-confidence, and self-assurance, making the learning process interesting and creating a serious interest in scientific knowledge among students. It was determined that the independent "discovery" of the law of truth ensures that the acquired knowledge is not forgotten. Even if independently generated knowledge is forgotten, it can be quickly restored.⁵

Implementation of independent education, or student independent work, which is an important component of it, based on a well-planned program, is of great importance in the formation of free thinking. To increase the effectiveness of independent education and organize independent work of students in subjects outside the classroom, especially in the first courses, is crucial. Independent learning can take many forms, including online courses, attending seminars and conferences, or reading books and articles. Of course, independent learning requires discipline and self-motivation.

Supervising your studies will help you reach your full potential as a student and achieve your personal and professional goals.⁶ What is the main difference between independent work at the university and other types of work? This is the activity of the student who performs the task independently without the direct participation of the teacher.⁷ Additional features of this type of work are as follows: the existence of a problematic task that needs to be solved; the estimated time to complete the work; mental action in the process of finding a solution; activity of a conscious and independent approach by the student. Often, the goals of students' independent work are determined by the teacher.

Depending on the topic being studied and the level of complexity, they may differ, but the main ones, as a rule, are as follows: consolidation and systematization of the knowledge gained in the educational process; formation of the ability to work effectively with scientific literature and other sources of information; independent acquisition of knowledge and practical application; formation of critical thinking, analytical and research skills; development of time planning and organization skills; development of self-control and work evaluation skills.

Independent work can address the following tasks: repetition of covered material; deepening and acquisition of new knowledge; integration of theoretical information; summarizing and systematizing what has been learned; formation of practical skills and professional competencies; applying knowledge in practice; and solving specific tasks or situations. Lev Semyonovich Vygotsky emphasizes the importance of considering not only the types but also the levels of these tasks in students' independent work. The main methodological principles of independent work include purposefulness, consistency, regularity, logical structure, comfort, and scientific rigor.

Therefore, the goals and objectives of independent work, which the teacher announces in advance and the student refines during the process, should align with these principles. Independent work can vary based on location and the nature of tasks. For example, classroom and non-classroom activities differ by location. However, based on the nature of assignments, there are more types of independent work, each with distinct educational goals: preliminary study of the material; listening to lectures and completing notes; working with recommended information sources; performing special tasks within the curriculum; preparing for tests and seminars; writing and defending essays or research papers; delivering presentations at conferences and seminars; preparing lectures and scientific studies; and analyzing scientific studies and monographs on the subject.

Traditionally, all types of tasks are divided into three levels: reproductive, productive, and creative. The reproductive level focuses on reinforcing existing knowledge and includes tasks such as reading various literary sources, completing and studying outlines, and solving problems that the student can address independently. The productive level involves direct engagement with new material and aims to deepen knowledge and strengthen practical skills and competencies. Tasks at this level include planning the structure of a book, creating bibliographic lists, developing diagrams, preparing oral and written answers to questions, and evaluating the written works of peers.⁸

5 Khudoynazarova M.F. Formation of students' creativity in the process of independent learning. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. April 2023, Issue 4

6 Yuldashev Sh.I. The importance and role of independent learning of students in the modern educational process // Methodological manual. - T.: UzMU, 2022.- 15 p.

7 Karimova D.R. Independent learning in the credit-module system // Methodological manual. -Tashkent: OOO "Complex Print", 2021. 15 p.

8 Khusainov R.R. The role of independent learning in improving the quality of teaching subjects in higher education // Modern Education. 2016. No. 4. 25p.

Creative level. The goals and tasks of independent work at the creative level are to independently seek knowledge, demonstrate the ability to think independently and analyze, as well as work with large and complex material. Tasks at this level: preparation of abstract; write an essay; conducting research; collecting material and writing a thesis; report preparation and protection. When choosing the level of independent work, it should be remembered that it should increase each time. It strengthens self-confidence and increases professionalism. It is important to teach students to always work independently, so it is very important to manage autonomous work. Students plan their own independent research and work regularly and continuously on specific learning tasks under the guidance of the teacher. There are various types of independent work, all of which help to improve students' creative abilities. Writing an essay, term paper, or other type of document has a unique position in independent creative research.

A term paper or a scientific report is a creative independent work that shows how knowledgeable and competent a student is. It involves a lot of hard and creative research on the part of students, as well as a clear, understandable and logical presentation of their knowledge in writing. It shows how knowledgeable, responsible and skilled a student is in expressing his/her opinion. The correct distribution of students' time is also important when doing independent work. Therefore, it is necessary for students to learn to plan and determine the sequence of their execution in terms of the importance and duration of the work to be performed.⁹

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Control of the student's independent work is carried out by the professor-teacher based on the schedule developed in the department and the technological map of the subject. Types of control of student independent work and criteria for its evaluation are developed and approved by the scientific council of the faculty. During independent education, students work on themselves and try to develop themselves. Through these actions, the level of education of students increases. They reach the level where they can apply the knowledge they have acquired throughout their life. The formation of independent learning skills plays a key role in the acquisition of in-depth knowledge and skills of students in the system of educational creative training. Independent education develops independent thinking and independent work in students.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated on October 8, 2019 № DP-5847, "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/6971334>
2. O.A. Koysinov, N.A. Muslimov. The Theory and Methodology of Organizing Independent Education in the Preparation of Vocational Education Teachers. Monograph. - T.: "Fan," 2009. - 92 p.
3. Sh.I. Yoldashev. The Importance and Place of Independent Education of Students in the Modern Educational Process. Methodological Guide. - T.: UzMU, 2022. - 41 p.
4. D.R. Karimova. Independent Education in the Credit-Module System. Methodological Guide. - Tashkent: OOO "Simplex Print," 2021. - 126 p.
5. R.R. Husainov. The Role of Independent Education in Improving the Quality of Teaching Subjects in Higher Education. Modern Education. 2016. No. 4. - P. 25-32.
6. G.N. Ibrahimova. Development of Creative Thinking in Students by Means of Interactive Technologies in the Higher Education System. Modern Education. 2017. No. 4. - P. 30-35.
7. M.F. Khudoyazarova. Formation of Students' Creativity in the Process of Independent Education. "Science and Education" Scientific Journal. April 2023. No. 4.

⁹ Karimova D.R. Independent learning in the credit-module system // Methodological manual. -Tashkent: OOO "Complex Print", 2021. 60 p.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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